

The Data Infrastructure of the German Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie: An Enabling Intermediary between Raw Data and Analysis

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Abstract

Academic data infrastructures facilitate bibliometric research and reporting, as they link bibliometric data with research interests. In Germany the *Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie (KB)*, a national consortium of more than 20 institutions, serves this purpose by hosting, probing, and curating large-scale bibliometric raw data from commercial and open providers. Users at partner institutions regularly apply the data infrastructure in workflows. Due to its former focus on commercial data, the KB's infrastructure has not been detailed transparently to date. However, as an increasing number of bibliometric publications and reports rely upon it, this article provides a comprehensive documentation of the KB's infrastructure specifically designed for bibliometric applications. It explains the conceptual considerations employed to define the infrastructure's technical characteristics and procedures. Descriptions are provided regarding (1) the technical infrastructure, (2) the KB's own database schema consistently applied across several bibliometric databases, (3) processing bibliometric raw data, (4) multi-dimensional quality assurance processes, and (5) additional data curation. By making these procedures transparent and open to scrutiny, we aim to bolster the reliability of our infrastructure and facilitate reproducible research while

contributing to the broader discourse on transparency in the field of bibliometrics and providing input to other organisations developing similar infrastructures.

1. Introduction

Bibliometrics can significantly support analyses of the science system and evaluation of research performance through indicators, analyses, and consultation. Increased demand for these information and services underscores the importance of the reliability of the data and indicators used. The meaningful and valid use of bibliometric methods therefore requires a technical infrastructure, accompanying bibliometric research, and a critical examination of the methodological possibilities and limitations. To build up such capacities in Germany, several bibliometric research groups and the national Federal Ministry for Education and Research in 2008 established – and enhanced ever since – an infrastructure to support bibliometric research and reporting among German research institutions. The resulting *Kompetenznetzwerk Bibliometrie* (KB, Competence Network Bibliometrics¹) currently constitutes a network of more than 20 partner institutions. These partners engage in bibliometric research and service projects based on a shared data infrastructure, competence development, and exchange activities within and beyond the network. Key functions such as the technical hosting, data processing, and administration are distributed across several member institutions, while other member institutions with their diverse backgrounds and interests focus more on bibliometric research and services.

The data infrastructure with its licensed proprietary data can be described as the motivating core of the KB and is therefore a central component of the network's activities and outcomes. In addition to facilitating access to costly commercial bibliometric data, the data infrastructure supports bibliometric research and service projects by conducting the essential work to prepare the bibliometric data for analysis in a centralised manner, which otherwise every KB user would need to do by themselves. The processing of the licensed bibliometric raw data into a format directly applicable for bibliometric analyses with an accompanying 24/7 availability of the analytical service allows KB users to directly focus on their research interest without the need to deal with the technical and legal requirements. Furthermore, the delivered raw data is extensively scrutinised for potential quality issues and structural changes that might affect bibliometric research. Users are informed about data issues or changes and may make use of KB's own metadata, which extends the commercial data and standardises it between sources. Conducting this bibliometric groundwork centrally within the KB and drawing on the various specializations of the KB partner institutions allows reuse and prevents unnecessary duplication of this work by the users and enables a quality-assured and informed use of the data.

To date, the KB has relied on the commercial bibliometric databases Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus to progress its mission, primarily due to a lack of open alternatives and the currently superior data quality of these sources. While this data has been studied extensively and proven useful for many applications, its proprietary nature has confined KB's activities. As dissemination of the proprietary data is prohibited by the licence terms, the KB has been restricted in the type and amount of information about its data infrastructure that it may share with non-partners. Consequently, general principles of open science (Birkle et al., 2020) cannot be complied with

¹ <http://www.bibliometrics-network.de>

(e.g. Wilkinson et al., 2016; Bilder et al., 2020), but also more bibliometric-focused meta-frames like the Leiden Manifesto cannot be fulfilled completely (e.g., Hicks et al., 2015, p. 430: “Keep data collection and analytical processes open, transparent and simple”).

Recently, a number of open or semi-open systems have emerged in the field of scientific information retrieval, which could also be used for bibliometric purposes and enable new possibilities for the KB, including expanding its infrastructure: e.g., OpenAlex (Priem et al., 2022), Semantic Scholar (Ammar et al., 2018), OpenCitations (Peroni et al., 2017), Open Research Knowledge Graph (Jaradeh et al., 2019), or OpenAIRE research graph (Manghi et al., 2019). A transparent documentation of the data, technical structures and/or computational methods is common for these open data infrastructures and technical services (apart from those mentioned above, see also e.g. Di Giambattista et al., 2022; Robinson-Garcia et al., 2017), curated open data sources (e.g., Marx & Fuegi, 2019; Vrandečić & Krötzsch, 2014; Pellissier Tanon et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2023) or research infrastructures (e.g., Darch et al., 2020; Wulf et al., 2021). While both WoS and Scopus have also recently issued publications describing their products (Birkle et al., 2020; Baas et al., 2020), the structures, procedures and heuristics applied by academic bibliometric centres to host, process and enrich proprietary bibliometric data are usually ‘closed-box’, so that even among institutions with comparable licences, it is not trivial to replicate results directly.

We therefore want to ‘open up’ the KB. Apart from hosting, probing and curating open bibliometric data to overcome the limitations of using proprietary data for bibliometric research and reporting, we also render the internal structures of, and processes behind, the KB’s bibliometric data infrastructure transparent to publicly document the specific handling of the data in the KB as a prerequisite to becoming an open bibliometric infrastructure. This facilitates the open sharing of details regarding how the data behind any paper or report created using the KB’s bibliometric data infrastructure are generated. Furthermore, content and methodological pluralism is arguably advantageous for scientific progress, as it hedges against potential dead ends, allows rapid switches to more productive scientific paths and increases the robustness of results. The same reasoning can be extended to bibliometric infrastructures, as, for example, implemented data formats (e.g., SQL data schemas), definitions (e.g., citation indicators) or classifications (e.g., discipline or research topic classifications) will shape to some degree the prospects of subsequent bibliometric research or reporting. This principle should thus also apply to bibliometric infrastructures as important tools for research in bibliometrics and related fields. The evolutionary path of infrastructures provides valuable insights into productive and beneficial set-ups. Transparency-driven mutual learning would support the overall effectiveness and efficiency of these infrastructures in fulfilling their individual mission following the lines of open science reasoning. Hence, this paper also invites an exchange about the diverse methodological settings in bibliometric infrastructures.

2. Objectives and Design Principles of the Infrastructure

2.1. Central objectives

The primary objective of developing the KB’s data infrastructure was to initiate and facilitate bibliometric research and services through a technical framework that acts as an intermediary

between raw data and its application in bibliometric research and service. The fundamental rationale behind establishing such infrastructure was to facilitate the usage of bibliometric raw data by researchers by lowering the barriers for using this large-scale and – technically and theoretically – complex data. The compilation of bibliometric metadata from thousands of journals owned largely by private publishers generates an analytical value that private database providers commercialise nowadays via subscriptions to ready-made web platforms. However, the resulting black box of these web services hampers data transparency requirements and restricts usage. The KB therefore purchases raw bibliometric data from Clarivate (WoS) and Elsevier (Scopus). Working with raw data increases both (1) the transparency of processes and derived metrics, such as pre-calculated indicators and (2) the users’ analytical capacity through greater flexibility. Open bibliometric data will allow the KB to progress even further in this direction. As such, the KB has recently started to incorporate OpenAlex by OurResearch into its offerings.

2.2. Design principles

The KB data processing of the raw data into a user-friendly format is governed by several principles, which facilitate a flexible and broad usage.

Centralised data provision adapted to local needs: While a centralised data infrastructure requires users from the diverse KB partner institutions to adapt to a separate analytical environment, it allows them to make instant use of sufficiently powerful and tailored computational resources. The KB’s centralised computation system aims to:

- facilitate large-scale analysis,
- secure the data protection of proprietary data,
- adapts to users’ needs by allowing the integration of local data and offering a variety of analytical programming languages.

These requirements are currently met by a central SQL database server and a general-purpose server as a programming interface. In the former, all users have private table spaces in which they can upload external data and share this data and results from database queries with other users. The powerful technical configuration of the server facilitates large-scale analyses beyond the capacity of users’ own computers and the centrally controlled technical infrastructure safeguards the proprietary data. The general-purpose server allows the upload of external data and usage of various programming languages for analyses to better adapt to users’ needs.

Ensuring analytical flexibility through SQL: The current number of KB users, at over 100 from more than 20 German institutions with diverse backgrounds and research interests, necessitates a flexible analytical infrastructure. The KB provides the data as a PostgreSQL database, which is characterised by the ease of counting operations with flexible grouping (typical for bibliometric applications), and offers a wide range of implemented statistical functions. SQL is a suitable base technology as the language is an ISO standard since 1987 [1] and thus works almost identically across database software systems. It is relatively easy to learn and widely taught at universities and there are vast knowledge resources online to support users. According to the Stack Overflow Developer Survey, SQL is one of the most popular languages [2]. Modern SQL systems also integrate complete procedural programming languages, in our case Postgres’ native PL/pgSQL as

well as third party languages, which facilitate common programming tasks like bulk record processing without having to export the data from the database. Conversely, analytical programming languages like Python or R also integrate interfaces to SQL servers. Optimised database indices allow for fast information retrieval operations and custom datasets can be exported to general-purpose computers within the KB. Another advantage of SQL is that queries against defined databases can easily be enriched with custom datasets. However, the SQL service presents somewhat of a barrier for less tech-savvy users, as other point-and-click web services would allow an easier start but offer less flexibility overall. As such, the KB SQL service serves a target group who benefits from the additional flexibility and is willing to take on the extra work to overcome the entrance barrier.

Focusing on relevant data: Bibliometric raw data, as process data of scientific communication, holds a great wealth of depth. However, it is sometimes of technical nature or of only limited applicability for bibliometric analysis. To allow users to focus on their analytical interests without having to grapple with all the data fields, the KB preselects the most relevant data fields in its standard data provision – the so-called *Bibliometriedatenbank* (BDB – Bibliometric Database) – but allows supplementary access to all data fields in an additional repository – the so-called *Rohdatenbank* or *Rohdatenrepositorium* (RDB – Raw Database or Raw Data Repository). This balance between information overload and data austerity is continuously optimised to account for new data fields provided in the raw data. The RDB makes the delivered XML files accessible within the SQL database. In contrast, the BDB optimises data for usage by the KB members by transferring content of the delivered XML files into the KB’s own database schema. For each BDB version there is a corresponding RDB version maintaining the complete unaltered original record for enrichment projects and reproducibility. This combined approach facilitates the use of standardised and optimised data via the BDB and allows users to trace the processed data back to the raw data in the RDB, if required.

Facilitating database comparisons for analytical width: Bibliometric data sources vary in their indexation policy, scope of metadata, data quality and data provision. The respective data corpora of WoS, Scopus, and, as of recently, OpenAlex available in the KB data infrastructure are not merged, but each transferred to separate SQL databases, each with a standardised schema across databases, so that users can easily transfer queries from one database to another and thus readily compare and cross-check results in different sources. Hence, the diverse databases are understood as offering distinct perspectives on the science system and this variety is an important asset for analytical width.

Probing and enhancing data quality: An informed usage of bibliometric data also requires information on the data quality, especially given the proprietary database providers’ natural tendency to promote their products’ virtues, while being less explicit about their inherent drawbacks. Therefore, KB engages in an extensive quality assurance process, which also results in developments of data additions based on its expertise in the German science system (e.g., (Donner et al., 2020; Donner, 2017; Stahlschmidt & Schmidt, 2019; Schmidt, 2018; Olensky et al., 2016).

Balancing the need for current data and reproducibility: Bibliometric raw data is updated and extended weekly (or in some cases even daily) by the data providers. While these expansions allow

analysis of the latest research, the high frequency of change also hinders collaboration and reproducibility of bibliometric analyses. The KB therefore provides stable quarterly snapshots of the ingested bibliometric data to enable working with current data while at the same time facilitating collaboration among its members. The April version is considered the primary snapshot, as it covers nearly the complete previous publication year without excessive delay. As a long-term-stable (LTS) version, these April snapshots are archived for long-term reproducibility after two years. In contrast, the other quarterly snapshots are considered intermediate versions and as such, are only available for six months and are not archived to avoid overburdening IT resources. Providing quarterly versions also facilitates an agile infrastructure development to fine-tune and enhance the processing of the yearly LTS April version.

3. Analytical Infrastructure

The KB's analytical infrastructure is built according to the general design principles described above. As shown in the schematic diagram in Figure 1, the two central components of the infrastructure are the PostgreSQL server and a script server to run programs and scripts against the database from within the same local network. The systems in this network are accessible via an SSL VPN, against which registered users authenticate themselves with personalised credentials. Authorisation – for example, the permissions for certain schemas in PostgreSQL – takes place in the respective underlying systems. By adjusting permissions, users can share data within their personal table space with other KB users, e.g., within their institution or anyone in the system.

There are three different scenarios in which KB users can work with the data in the infrastructure. The most common is to work directly with the databases in PostgreSQL using locally installed clients. This is typically an SQL client tool like DBeaver or other program that can access the databases through the network port opened by the VPN tunnel, e.g., a Java program, the statistics package R, or a visualisation tool. The second scenario is to open a terminal session on the script server and run the programs (R, Java, Python or Perl) and tools (psql) that access the databases from there. The third scenario is to start a remote desktop session with NoMachineRX on the script server, allowing GUI-based applications to be used from the remote desktop. The advantage of the latter two scenarios is that long running programs or queries are independent of an open VPN connection. Users can log in later in a new VPN session and return to their processes and result sets.

The PostgreSQL database runs on a powerful Linux server with two local disk arrays in RAID 5 configuration, one with SSDs and one with HDDs. There is also storage on two different NAS systems. The latest and most important bibliometric databases are stored on local SSDs for performance reasons. There are two PostgreSQL instances running; one for production and one for development. In the production instance, all bibliometric databases and all personal users are organised as schemas that reside in a single PostgreSQL database to ease data sharing among users. We discussed and tested several options for the logical structure, but the one we finally chose

offers advantages both in terms of system administration and usability. The resulting usage of the analytical infrastructure is monitored and reported on the KB website².

An important and helpful part of the infrastructure is a Confluence wiki that is used within the KB for documentation purposes, for KB internal communication, and for sharing knowledge. We use the comment function of wiki pages, the blog feature and a wiki-based Q&A tool to inform about events, discuss topics, support users, and document the systems, databases, mapping and QA processes, etc. In addition to the wiki, we use a service desk tool (Matrix42) for the handling of service requests (such as setting up accounts) and incident notifications.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of KB’s analytic infrastructure

4. Data Sources

Empirical results of bibliometric analyses are not solely defined by the research questions and its technical and methodological implementation, but also reflect the databases’ underlying characteristics, which can substantially affect results (Stahlschmidt & Stephen, 2022). As structural differences between databases thus represent divergent perspectives on the science system, the KB utilises bibliometric raw data in its offerings and makes use of several competing data sources in parallel. Data of different providers is loaded into SQL databases with the same database schema. The diversity of databases offered by the KB is thus an analytical asset for its users to match their requirements with an appropriate database and compare results between databases.

² <https://bibliometrie.info/en/research/working-reports/>

Since its launch, the KB has been working with the data products WoS and Scopus, as these have established themselves as the two leading databases for bibliometric research and services (e.g., Pranckutė, 2021). While the few providers of multidisciplinary large scale bibliometric databases like Clarivate and Elsevier can address all potential raw data clients in a coordinated way, the multiplicity of clients results in a higher coordination effort on their side leading to an information imbalance between the selling providers and the purchasing clients. Hence KB centralises the licences for its partners and is thus able to take a more active role in the negotiations.

The implications arising from the proprietary nature of the licensed databases WoS and Scopus have also motivated the current efforts of ‘opening’ the KB and engagement with new open data sources. Apart from the obvious advantages of better access and reproducibility, there are other relevant aspects to integrating open data sources: There is long-standing criticism (e.g. Van Leeuwen et al., 2001; Van Raan et al., 2011) that both WoS and Scopus are biased against non-English language research and research not conducted in Western countries, limiting the analytical potential of KB’s users. However, in the case of new, less curated, openly available databases, questions arise regarding the quality of the content, respectively the degree of internal consistency. In order to support users with data of the best quality, KB engages in a constant monitoring of bibliometric databases including the currently supported databases and emerging candidates, such as Digital Science’s Dimensions (Taubert & Lenke, 2022; Scheidt & Meier, 2022; Stahlschmidt & Stephen, 2022).

4.1 Supported bibliometric databases

4.1.1. Web of Science

WoS, formerly Web of Knowledge, is the oldest multidisciplinary citation database (Birkle et al., 2020). Its main component, the Science Citation Index, was introduced in 1964 by the Institute of Scientific Information. It has since been acquired and is currently operated by Clarivate. As of February 2024, the *WoS Core Collection* comprised over 91 million records and its 2.19 billion cited references extended back to 1900 [3]. The Core Collection covers all disciplines, but its coverage is strongest in the physical, health, and life sciences (Visser, van Eck & Waltman, 2021). The WoS Core Collection, i.e. without its recent extension by regional indices and the Emerging Source Citation Index (ESCI), is smaller than alternative publicly available databases, as its inclusion policy is more selective. According to the provider, certain citation-based and content-related quality criteria are applied (e.g., existence of a peer review policy, scientific content and adherence to community standards, but also journal impact [4]). The newer ESCI or the various regional indices represent efforts by Clarivate to diversify its content beyond core journals. The KB licenses several WoS indices: Science Citation Index Extended (SCIE), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) and Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI), jointly termed WoS Primary by Clarivate, as well as the Science and Social Sciences Conference Proceedings Citation Indexes (CPCI-S/SSH). The coverage extends from 1980 to present for early KB members, and from 2000 to present for newer users, which is implemented via PostgreSQL Views.

4.1.2. Scopus

Scopus was launched in 2004 by Elsevier (Baas et al., 2020). As of January 2024, it covered over 94 million records and over 2.4 billion references dating back to 1970 [5], and thus is of comparable size to WoS. Scopus is curated by independent subject matter experts (Scopus Content Selection and Advisory Board) based on citation-based and (less clearly defined) qualitative criteria. Journal admissions are also regularly re-evaluated, e.g., in response to concerns or complaints about publication standards [6]. Like WoS, Scopus has more extensive coverage of the physical, health, and life sciences than the social sciences and humanities (Visser, et al., 2021). The KB licenses the *All ANI (Abstract and Indexing) since 1996, All Author Profiles and Citation counts*.

4.1.3. OpenAlex

OpenAlex is a “free and open catalog of the global research system” [7] released on 1 January 2022 by OurResearch as a replacement for the discontinued Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) (Priem et al., 2022). Scheidsteger & Haunschild (2023) have confirmed that OAL is de facto a continuation and extension of MAG, whereby the core bibliographic metadata has been retained and, in the case of document type specifications, even improved. Patents that were part of MAG are, however, not included in OpenAlex. OpenAlex comprised 243 million documents (referred to as “works”) and 1.9 billion references as of early 2024 and offers monthly open snapshots of the complete dataset for download or via an API. Since 2023, several KB partners have been working jointly on a detailed evaluation of the data in terms of quality and usability (e.g., Culbert et al., 2024).

5. Bibliometric Database Schema

The KB database schema is an integral part of the data infrastructure as it serves as an interface between the data and the user. As the users access the data via the data schema, it has a decisive influence on the user experience. It is therefore continuously optimised by the corresponding KB working group, taking into account new metadata and evolving user interest by incorporating user feedback via surveys. When adapting the schema, several – sometimes competing – aims are considered and a balance is struck between them. The foremost principle is that the relational table schema supports typical bibliometric applications, i.e. it should support users in conducting their empirical analyses. Second, it holds the necessary level of abstraction to be applicable for several distinct data sources to enable their parallel usage. Third, the schema is designed to increase usage performance. Finally, it targets usability by rendering specific metadata easily findable. These aims have guided the following principles of the present design:

- In line with the central aim of supporting typical bibliometric applications, the database comprises pre-computed key paper-level citation indicators and verified identifiers to link to other data.
- An identical schema is provided for KB’s supported databases listed above. There is one common table structure for WoS, Scopus, and OpenAlex but depending on the available data not all columns can be populated for all databases. While all databases are kept separately in different database schemas, users can thus always write queries which work across data sources to ease the application of the diverse sources.

- Query performance is prioritised over normalisation and storage requirements, i.e. some data is stored redundantly to reduce the number of costly join operations and allow for faster analysis.
- Advanced features of PostgreSQL are used to improve performance and to keep the overall structure of the schema simple. This includes the use of (1) array data types (for entities with possibly more than one value) and custom enumerated types (for entities with a fixed, very limited number of possible values), (2) full-text indexing of text data, (3) table partitioning, and (4) table clustering using indexes on identifiers to improve access speed.
- The metadata of publications and the complex relationships within the data, such as those between publications, their authors, and their affiliations are, similar to a laboratory approach, broken down into its components to facilitate the use of this information.
- To reduce complexity for the user, rarely used data is omitted in the schema but can always be accessed in the XML-based RDB. This also reduces processing costs.
- Data documentation and usage advice are included in the database schema as table and column comments to allow a direct access to essential context information.
- For pragmatic and safety reasons, tables in the schema are provided as read-only, so users only apply read and analytical operations, saving outcomes in their personal schema.

The core tables consist mainly of the bibliographic metadata at the document level with light processing and validation checks. Data derived via the application of algorithms, e.g., author or institution disambiguation, are provided in separate tables. These additional tables form a separate outer layer, as they offer several, often competing perspectives on the core data. This approach enables the comparative application of several algorithmic solutions and makes a transparent distinction between document- and algorithmic-based metadata with their different levels of validity.

The core of the schema consists of separate but linked tables for the main metadata entities available for each indexed publication, i.e. information on the items themselves (`items` table), the authors (`items_authors`), the corresponding affiliations comprising all affiliations (`items_affiliations`) or only those with direct links to authors (`authors_affiliations`) to make explicit the presence or absence of author-affiliation link information, respectively, as the case may be in the original data. Additional tables contain references (`refs`), the publication venue (`issn_isbn`), the publisher (`publishers`) and funder information (`funding_agencies_grants`). Separate tables for each entity allow for various conceptual entry points into the data, e.g., a comparative analysis on funders via a query start at the funder table or a publication analysis for a particular institution via a query start at the `items_affiliations` table. Hence, the KB data schema structure mimics the analytical entities users might think of to ease the translation process of an abstract research question interest into a specific SQL query. In addition, breaking down metadata into its components allows for flexible re-combinations that enhance the analytical potential.

In detail, the central `items` table includes bibliographic data such as publication title, volume, issue, page data, language, identifiers (database-internal ID, DOI, PubMed ID), and open access status data. It also contains data that, in a fully normalised design, would be in separate tables but that are convenient to have in the same table to avoid costly join operations, e.g., source title,

author keywords, and journal subject classification data. More detailed publication date information is also available in the `items` table, namely online publishing date, and a newly introduced publication date that combines the regular and advance online date into one indicator of the earliest publication year, and publication month. The latter gives users the option to compute more temporally precise citation counts, which eliminates the citation advantage of publications published earlier in a year over those published later in the same year by forming equally long citation windows (Donner, 2018).

The separate tables for data on abstracts, cited references, publisher data, serials and book standard numbers, and grant funding data are mostly linked to the `items` table by the vendor item identifier as a foreign key. For entities pertaining to one publication record, whenever possible the order of listing of entities in the original source publication is preserved and explicitly represented in the tables. For example, the author order and reference list order are stored as numeric variables and allow unique identification of each author or cited reference according to original order in a publication record, which is important for various bibliometric applications. The `author` table also contains external author IDs (ORCID).

The DDL script for the database schema is made publicly accessible on Zenodo³.

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/12206867>

Figure 2: Core tables of the BDB schema (without additional tables such as those for the disambiguation of institutions)

6. Data Processing

6.1. Delivery Schedules and Processing

Figure 3: Workflow for setting up raw data repositories (RDB coded as “rep”) and bibliometric databases (BDB coded as “b”) for WoS

While bibliometric raw data is updated with high frequency by the database providers, the KB provides quarterly snapshots of supported bibliometric databases to balance the need for current data with reproducibility and collaboration requirements. Snapshots of the respective state of the data are taken in January as an early peek in the previous publication year; April as the primary snapshot with the best balance between timeliness and sufficient coverage (i.e. >90%) of the

previous publication year; July as a more stable view of the previous publication year and first glimpse into the current publication year; and finally October as an intermediate state advanced upon the July snapshot. In order to meet this schedule, which is also motivated by the bibliometric custom to analyse complete publication years (e.g., for citation normalisation), the delivery of the raw data, as well as the KB-internal processing has been organised accordingly.

In the case of the WoS data, the KB receives weekly delta updates and one yearly snapshot of all subscribed WoS Indices (usually at the end of February). Apart from serving as a new baseline for the quarterly updates in each new year, the annual files might contain additional content for old items not available in the regular update files (such as Citation Topics data), therefore we start from scratch with the annual files, as shown in Figure 3. The full snapshot is used as the starting point for a new RDB, which will then be updated on a weekly basis (“wos_rep”). This ingestion of the weekly updates into the RDB enables KB users who require up-to-date data to access the just delivered data, although it is neither processed nor quality checked. In case of a new delivery of an already existing item (identifiable with the identifier given by the data provider), the old item will be overwritten with the new version.

For every quarterly snapshot, a copy of this up-to-date RDB is taken at the end of the respective quarter (e.g., end of January 2023 for “wos_rep_202301”). This snapshot then forms the basis for the respective BDB snapshot by mapping the content of the RDB to the BDB (e.g., “wos_b_202301”), in accordance with the KB’s database schema detailed above. This process is described in more detail in the following section. Clarivate delivers WoS raw data in XML format. For the RDB, the XML format is retained and written directly to a single PostgreSQL table using Java. Additional data available only in the annual files are extracted from the XML and kept in a separate table in the RDB so that it is not overwritten by the weekly updates. For Scopus data, Elsevier sends the KB four data deliveries per year, from which we generate four time-specific RDB and BDB versions per year. In the beginning of May of each year, Elsevier supplies us with one complete snapshot of Scopus data up to the end of April (‘annual files’). They also provide three update files at the end of July, October, and January. Incorporating major Scopus updates via quarterly snapshots has resulted in less stress on the KB processing pipeline compared to the former mode of incorporating sometimes very large weekly updates. Scopus raw data is provided as XML data, which we write directly to a PostgreSQL schema using Java. Upon receiving the annual files, these files are used as the baseline for the year’s annual and quarterly RDBs and the updates are added to this base file. Hence the quarterly RDB is built from the annual files for the April version and plus the consecutive updates supplied in July, October and January. As with WoS, these RDBs are mapped to the BDBs. The data deliveries described above are those that are planned. However, there might be additional deliveries of files for additions and corrections in the data for both WoS and Scopus.

We began integrating OpenAlex into the KB infrastructure in 2023. In the case of OpenAlex, we use monthly complete snapshots to generate at least four versions of each of the RDB and BDBs per year, and at most 12 as OpenAlex releases updates monthly. Here we keep one stable version for a specific long-term project and delete versions according to (lack of) demand, with the principle of having at least two quarterly versions available in parallel. OpenAlex data is obtained

as snapshots in JSONL files in a S3 bucket⁴. Python scripts are provided to load the data in a SQL database, and a PostgreSQL schema is also suggested. We initially used the given schema and the scripts – and continue to use them for the RDB – but we have since adapted and further developed both the scripts and schema according to the KB’s requirements for the BDB. As OpenAlex data evolves rapidly, some development effort has been required from the KB with every release so far to adapt to changes in the schema, new attributes, data format changes, and so on.

6.2. Mapping Content to the KB's Database Schema

The task of assigning data elements from the raw data to tables and columns in the BDB schema, in some cases after further processing, is referred to as ‘mapping’. Transferring the differently formatted raw data of the supported bibliometric data sources to the common KB database schema facilitates an instant usage by KB users, as the KB manages the particularities of the delivered data, allowing users to focus on their research interest via the harmonised format. As the raw data format differs between the supported sources (i.e. WoS, Scopus, and OpenAlex), each dataset requires its own mapping. A good understanding of and experience with the contents and definitions in each dataset is required to extract the desired information, as the content to be fed into the BDB schema is provided in different ways, with different names and different definitions for the data sources. Experience with the data sources also aids in the early detection of errors or mapping problems as well as the ability to address user requirements.

Mapping decisions must take into account various aspects of the data, such as quality and user interests (learned via exchange with users, e.g., surveys), and the aim is therefore to find the most suitable solution for the respective data source. Furthermore, the mapping can also change over time as both the raw data format and user requirements evolve. Mapping details are therefore versioned with Git to keep track of the changes. The mapping used for a specific version is also added as a PostgreSQL table to the BDB schema so it can be readily accessed by users. All mappings were designed manually and are stored in a table with columns for BDB target table, BDB target column, raw data element and in addition comments, a heuristic or description of the reason for the mapping decision, the raw database query, and raw structure examples to allow reproducibility and tracking of the BDB data elements to the corresponding raw data source.

6.2.1. Relationship mapping between raw data and BDB

Often mapping consists of finding a value in the raw data and assigning it to a specific column in the BDB in a simple 1:1 relation. Take, for example, the column `organization` in the BDB table `items_affiliations`. In OpenAlex, `organization` is based on the element `display_name`, taken from the `institutions` object in the OpenAlex snapshot data⁵, the mapping of this metadata is thus 1:1. In the case of n:1 relationships, multiple parts of the XML data (elements/attributes, sometimes with conditions) are combined to populate a specific column in the BDB. In contrast to OpenAlex, in WoS⁵ and Scopus⁶, the XML raw format has different locations for ordinary and corresponding author addresses and, as not all corresponding/reprint addresses are contained in research addresses, both are combined for the column `organization` in `items_affiliations` to

⁴ <https://docs.openalex.org/download-all-data/openalex-snapshot>

⁵ <https://clarivate.libguides.com/c.php?g=593069&p=4117305>

fulfil any organization-focused user interest. The mapping also includes 1:n relationships, where a single element or attribute from the raw XML data is used to populate multiple tables or columns in the BDB. Taking up again the case of affiliations, research addresses are delivered with and without assignments to authors. These are stored separately in two BDB tables `items_affiliations` (all affiliations) and `authors_affiliations` (only affiliations with assignments to authors). This denormalization means that those address data that also comprise author links are in fact stored twice, again for the reason of having a simple and complete entry point for institutional queries (independent of author data) with `items_affiliations`.

6.2.2. Modification operations

The mapping process also comprises several operations that modify the data, use only parts of them or complement them:

Selection: In some cases, data are filtered before being used for the BDB to provide concise information. For example, the content may be supplied in other languages in addition to English, while only English values are required for a specific BDB column. These additional languages are thus filtered from the XML.

Derivation of data values: To simplify data usage, several common metrics are pre-calculated for users. First, this applies to aggregations, such as counts (of countries, pages, references and source references, organisations, authors per publication) or more complex values, such as pre-calculated citation indicators for each publication. Second, additional attributes are generated to provide further information, such as integer sequence numbers that indicate the order of elements in the XML. This is used, for instance, to represent the sequence of authors or affiliations. A third subtype involves the verification of data elements, requiring external information or tools, and the discarding of non-conforming values. For example, this includes calculating a check digit to validate ISSNs.

Standardisation: Standardisation of data simplifies the usage. First, we map certain data to codes that unify variants: for instance, the country coding provides a mapping of the contents in the raw data country element (e.g., 'German') to ISO codes (e.g., 'DEU'). As a result, not only countries but also federal states, counties, cities, provinces, universities, and other localities were mapped. When a new RDB is created, we look for countries that cannot be mapped according to the previous coding. Based on this list, the country coding is updated and then transferred to the BDB. According to the same principle as with the country codes, the original language of the documents in the database is marked with the ISO language code. For the original language, we use the German name in a lookup table to assign the language to the ISO code. For example, "Central Khmer", which means "Cambodian", is assigned the ISO Language Code "khm". Second, standardisation refers to procedures that ensure that all values in a column are formatted in the same way (e.g., upper/lower case, all ISSN values have a hyphen between the two four-digit sequences). A more challenging example is the splitting of author names. In the BDB we have separate columns for the first name and last name of an author for analytical flexibility. This structure is not always reliably present in the data sources; thus, we may have to split a string containing first name and last name into its components. While this sounds easy (and indeed is in

case the format is known), it can be challenging due to strings not following the documented format or cases in which the string does simply not contain a first name and a last name but e.g., a name of an author group.

7. Quality Assurance

The quality of bibliometric data is a key requirement for the data's information value. Hence the analyses of KB users depend on a sufficient level of data quality and transparency about this level, as both endow the analyses by KB users with credibility. Therefore, the KB engages in several data probing exercises in a centralised approach to allow users to focus on their research and account for any data quality issues identified. While the concept of data quality is multi-dimensional (International Organization for Standardization, 2008), the accuracy of the data constitutes the main concern in bibliometrics and motivates also KB's centralised quality assurance activities.

The primary logic of the quality assurance tests and procedures is to detect faulty or undesired behaviour in our processing tools, as well as problems that may arise from the heuristic mapping process that transfers delivered raw data into our PostgreSQL databases. Furthermore, we track data quality and development in close exchange with the data providers. We report bugs and changes in the data that may influence the bibliometric work and need specific interpretations. Depending on the nature and extent of the change, adaptations of the BDB schema may be required. Although some tests correspond more to checking our routines and other approaches more to tracing the source data quality, the analytical separation cannot be maintained throughout, since inadequate processing and mapping solutions may only become apparent through certain data changes. Our quality assurance routines are currently established for WoS and Scopus, with plans to fully incorporate OpenAlex in 2025. This will be based on a separate data quality analysis and data curation project for OpenAlex initiated in 2023 (e.g., Culbert et al., 2024). However, the quantitative recording of table contents is already in place for OpenAlex and the archiving of these data enables us to keep track of the data development from a long-term point of view.

As data quality issues, either inflicted by KB processing or sourced from the raw data, are initially unknown, the KB applies a range of complementing approaches to probe the data quality from different perspectives and thereby to increase the probability of uncovering potential issues. Hence, the KB's quality assurance is designed as a multi-layer approach with a technical starting point, data-logical and bibliometric theory-based heuristic tests in the middle and a bibliometric use-oriented end point covering a wide range of potential flaws:

Quantitative recording and temporal comparison of table contents (quarterly): For each database version, detailed statistics are created comparing numbers of table rows of the current version to the previous one. Each version's and row's numerical results are stored and a growth indicator is calculated. Selected comparison values of each new version with the previous one are visualised together with all previous values so that the patterns of potential variation over time can be visually analysed (and, if possible, related to changes related to the database schema or the data delivered). It is also checked whether columns contain null values, i.e. no data. These tests are automated and results and queries documented on wiki pages.

Content consistency through comparison with delivered raw data (quarterly): Detailed content checks are carried out for samples of around 2 million items from each BDB version. For this sample dataset, metadata of records in the BDB are compared to the corresponding metadata in the XML repository. The repository is queried with SQL XPath queries, which, as the BDB is loaded using Java programs, enables a double check of the loading process. For selected attributes (like countries, languages), complete value sets are extracted from the total amount of raw data and compared to the equivalent value set from the BDB.

Content consistency through data logical tests, monitoring of new data/modifications of the scheme (quarterly): A third type of quality assurance check focuses on the one hand on aggregated values, which are mostly calculated by the KB and in some cases delivered by data providers. It is checked whether aggregated values adhere to data-logical constraints and/or theoretical implications of the calculus. Examples for this approach include checking whether calculated or delivered aggregations, such as the reference count, correspond to the actual numbers of references, or how closely expected citation values approach the theoretically predicted values when aggregated across the entire database. On the other hand, we specifically try to identify and monitor potential anomalies in the data. The number of data anomalies, such as publication self-citations or citations prior to the publication year, is monitored over time.

In the event that new data are added by the data providers or changes/corrections are decided within the KB so that the mapping rules or the DB schema change, the correctness, consistency and dynamics of these data are tracked in detail over one or more versions. Detailed case checks for completeness and consistency, including comparisons with the XML data, are especially pursued when new data fields are supplied by the providers and incorporated into the database.

This approach is semi-automated. A report containing these tests (with attached queries), the visualisation resulting from the temporal comparison of the table contents and textual descriptions of data or schema changes or detected errors is made available to the KB user community via the wiki.

Application-level (macro) report (annually): This approach analyses the collective effects of potential changes in the data or its processing on the level of institutions, sectors, countries, and disciplines. Changes may arise not only from changes and additions by data providers, but also from the constant updating of institutional disambiguation of the KB, which influences sectoral trends, or the influence which national science policies may have on researchers' publication practices over time. This testing probes the key variables central to many bibliometric analyses to generate an overview of the current state of the databases and to highlight changes that may indicate data quality issues. The macro-level testing consists of a visually oriented comparison of key bibliometric indicators at national, sectoral, and field levels between the latest 10 years of data in the current and previous versions of each of the WoS and Scopus bibliometric database. Indicators include publication counts, mean normalised citation rates, rates of uncited publications, changes in the journals indexed, changes and missingness in items' metadata, changes in discipline classifications, and publications unassigned to disciplines, institutions or countries. New indicators may be introduced annually to target specific issues or expand the breadth of testing. The reports of this QA testing include a description of the indicator, what trends could be expected or might signal issues, and any pertinent information to interpreting the indicator. The processing is semi-

automated via use of an R Markdown project, streamlining production and ensuring reproducibility. The annual report is initially circulated to KB members who work very closely with the technical infrastructure and published afterwards on the KB website⁶.

For all approaches, any unexpected results are subsequently investigated to determine their cause and any necessary action to address potential issues is taken. This may include, for instance, discussions with the data providers, modifications to internal data processing in the KB, and dissemination of information to KB users. Particular topics of interest are presented at user meetings.

8. Data Enrichment and Curation

8.1. Disambiguation of Institutional Address Information

One key component of the KB infrastructure is the disambiguation of authors' institutional addresses within the supported databases (Winterhager et al., 2014; Donner et al., 2020). The rationale behind these activities is the insufficiency of address information provided by proprietary databases in this regard. Due to the KB's expertise in the German science system, address disambiguation is focused solely on the German research landscape. The KB infrastructure maintains a comprehensive list of currently 2,962 German research institutions and organisations, each associated with a preferential address name. Additionally, each organisation is categorised into at least one (in a few cases, more than one) sector of the German research landscape. The list of sectors includes but is not limited to universities, Max Planck institutes, Helmholtz centres, Fraunhofer institutes, institutes of the Leibniz association, and private companies.

The disambiguation process encompasses several steps. At its core, the process involves matching address strings from proprietary databases' affiliation data to the corresponding entries for German research institutions using a set of regular expression patterns. Subsequently, the disambiguated addresses are aggregated to the top level of institutions. Currently, the procedure employs 47,902 patterns for this task. The aggregation to the top level of research institutions implies that addresses are attributed to discrete legal entities rather than their subdivisions (e.g., university departments). However, due to resource constraints, not all address strings are assigned to an institution. The creation of regular expression patterns is guided by the frequency of address variations in the databases, resulting in approximately 6.18% (WoS) or 9.73% (Scopus) of not-disambiguated address data. It is worth noting that this approach may disproportionately affect organisations with limited publication outputs, such as private companies.

For different usage scenarios, the data is organised in two ways: the “current perspective”, in which the addresses are assigned to the facilities that exist today, and the “synchronous perspective”, which reflects the situation at the time of publication. Data for both modes are organised into separate tables for each database version, facilitating convenient usage. The distinction between the two perspectives underscores the dynamic nature of the institutional landscape and emphasises

⁶ <https://bibliometrie.info/en/research/working-reports/>

the need for ongoing efforts to keep the map of the German research landscape up to date during the disambiguation process.

Transitioning Address Disambiguation to an Open Environment: The development of the address disambiguation procedure commenced in 2008 with the establishment of the former Kompetenzzentrum Bibliometrie (Competence Center Bibliometrics), the predecessor of the current KB. Initially, address disambiguation was exclusively applied to the WoS and Scopus datasets. Since 2023, this situation has evolved with the advent of open data sources, particularly the emergence of OpenAlex. The transformations prompted by such developments can be characterised by ‘interoperability’ and ‘openness’. Firstly, the emergence of new data sources relevant to bibliometric analysis necessitates improved interoperability of address disambiguation. In response, persistent identifiers like ROR ID have been incorporated into the tables provided by the address disambiguation. Furthermore, efforts have been made to align basic data about German research institutions with official German statistics. Secondly, the address disambiguation procedure has been successfully applied to the new open bibliometric database, OpenAlex, during a test phase. Consequently, it is plausible that disambiguated address information will be regularly provided for open bibliometric data in the future. Given the utility of the address disambiguation procedure for address strings from other non-proprietary data sources, the KB plans to publish it under an open license.

8.2. Citation indicators

We calculate commonly used item-level citation impact indicators, such as citation counts for each item within 3, 5, and all years after publication. From these, normalised citation indicators are pre-calculated for the same three periods, namely citation scores and dichotomous 10% highly cited indicators normalised for publication year, document type, and field (using the vendor’s subject classification scheme). The difficulty of assigning multiple field assignments per publication for field-normalised citation scores is handled in accordance with the methodology described in Waltman et al. (2011), section 6. The provision of common indicators as data enrichment facilitates the use of data on the one hand and supports the reproducibility of results for research and reports through standardisation on the other. Further indicators with broad application potential are therefore likely to be added in the future.

9. Discussion

The KB data infrastructure constitutes the initiating core of the KB and is used extensively for research and reporting throughout Germany. However, the data infrastructure denotes only one building block of the KB and is complemented by further KB activities, which in their interaction support the bibliometric outcomes of the KB partners. For example, a knowledgeable use of the data infrastructure requires the users to hold bibliometric and science studies theory, as well as technical analytical skills. Hence, skill transfer is an essential KB activity allowing users to gain general bibliometric, and also KB-specific, skills to make use of the infrastructure. The KB organises various formats for discussions among users about analysis possibilities, limitations, the current state of research and desiderata, including an open research seminar. These communication

formats support the development of competence, and also serve as a feedback channel to optimise the data infrastructure in line with users' needs.

The increase in the number of users, as well as the growing interconnectedness of data infrastructure, knowledge transfer, and user exchange, was accompanied by a tenfold increase in publications by KB users in the bibliometric journals *Scientometrics*, *Journal of Informetrics*, *Quantitative Science Studies*, and *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* since the launch of the KB in 2008. Furthermore, an increasing number, if not all, of the bibliometric monitoring exercises of the German science system are at least partially based on data from the KB. Hence, the data infrastructure outlined above has become an essential tool for bibliometric research and reporting in Germany.

However, due to licence restrictions of the proprietary bibliometric databases, the reach of the KB has been constrained in the past: only users at formerly 7, nowadays 24, German partner institutions could be admitted to the licence contracts with Clarivate and Elsevier. Open bibliometric data, like OpenAlex, is currently being incorporated into the KB infrastructure to overcome these licence-based limitations. Open licences allow KB to incorporate more institutions in its data infrastructure and to share its own data openly with interested third parties. This measure will extend the range of the KB's data infrastructure, but probably also alter its nature. Instead of predominately focusing on and enhancing the information value of proprietary data for its users, the KB's own curational and enrichment work will take on a more prominent role, as it allows the KB to contribute to the ongoing transition to open bibliometric data.

Endnotes

[1] <https://www.iso.org/standard/16661.html>

[2] <https://survey.stackoverflow.co/2023/#technology-most-popular-technologies>

[3] <https://clarivate.libguides.com/webofscienceplatform/coverage>

[4] <https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/webofscience-platform/web-of-science-core-collection/editorial-selection-process/editorial-selection-process/>

[5] <https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content>

[6] <https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content/content-policy-and-selection>

[7] <https://help.openalex.org/>

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